

Life History of Retired Staff at Inifap, Veracruz, Mexico

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ABSTRACT: This research is focused on knowing the life histories of retired personnel of the general base-field tabulator who worked at INIFAP for the regulatory period, which is more than 30 years of service. The premise of the study is that there are specific cases where sometimes there are people who retire and enjoy their pension very little time because they die in the short time after that stage of retirement. The study was conducted with a naturalistic paradigm through a descriptive case study approach, and the prioritization of qualitative data focused on the life stories of people already retired from INIFAP. In this case, two people already retired some years ago from INIFAP and who were assigned to the Cotaxtla Experimental Field and identified in the document as Participant 1 and 2, respectively, participated. A script for the interviews, as well as an interview recorded with a high-end cell phone were used as instruments in the collection of life histories, in which the information was systematized by means of the aforementioned instrument and thus have the complete chronicle. With this research, it is intended that the approaches expressed in this article serve as support to those who have in their daily life will have similar situations to the one exposed and, specifically, so it is concluded that it was possible to identify several factors that motivated and at the same time satisfied the INIFAP field personnel who retired in previous years.

KEYWORDS: family, field activities, retirement, health, economy

INTRODUCTION

Theoretical contextualization of INIFAP. INIFAP is an Institution of scientific and technological excellence with leadership and national and international recognition for its capacity to respond to the demands of knowledge and technological innovations, through highly trained personnel with infrastructure, state-of-the-art tools and a modern and autonomous administration for the benefit of the forestry, agricultural and livestock subsectors, the Mexican countryside and society in general. Since its foundation in 1985, its priority has been the optimal use of material, human and budgetary resources, as well as the creation of synergies among research personnel, recognizing the interactions and complementarity to serve the country's producers (<https://www.gob.mx/inifap/que-hacemos>). INIFAP's main objective is to contribute to sustainable rural development by improving competitiveness and maintaining the natural resource base, through participatory and co-responsible work with other institutions and public and private organizations associated with the Mexican countryside, by generating scientific knowledge and technological innovation in agriculture and forestry, in response to the demands and needs of agroindustrial chains and different types of producers. Like any government institution, INIFAP's mandate is to contribute to sustainable rural development by generating scientific knowledge and technological innovation in agriculture and forestry in response to the demands and needs of agroindustrial chains

and different types of producers, improving competitiveness and maintaining the natural resource base, through participatory and co-responsible work with other institutions and public and private organizations associated with the Mexican countryside. INIFAP's mission is to develop technological solutions to promote innovation in the Mexican countryside, while its vision is to be a leading institution recognized for its technological solutions for the benefit of forestry, agricultural and livestock producers. INIFAP's institutional values are those that reflect the ideas and beliefs that express what we value as an Institution, in addition to supporting the Mission and further developing the organizational culture to achieve our Vision. These values are aligned with the Code of Ethics of the Federal Public Administration which are mentioned below: a) Welfare. Guarantee the effective exercise of economic, social, cultural and environmental rights, with emphasis on reducing inequality gaps and conditions of vulnerability and discrimination in populations and territories, b) Quality. Satisfy the requirements and expectations of clients, partners, users and beneficiaries, c) Reliability. To be a source of reliable information, that is, that the research and dissemination products generated by INIFAP are verifiable, d) Cooperation. Join efforts with other people or institutions, recognizing our strengths and weaknesses and the need to complement each other to achieve a common goal, e) Efficiency. To seek at all times the best use of human, material, technological and financial resources, f) Gender Equity. To guarantee that both women and men have access to public goods and services, to institutional programs and benefits, and to jobs, positions and commissions, under the same conditions, possibilities and opportunities, g) Spirit of Service. To meet the needs of society, in the areas of forestry, agricultural and livestock production, with honesty and equity, h) Honesty. To behave with integrity in accordance with professional ethics and responsibility as public servants, i) Integrity. Act in a congruent manner with the principles, values and rules of integrity that must be observed and complied with in the performance of their employment, position, commission or function, firmly convinced in the commitment to adjust their conduct to INIFAP's culture, being intolerable any act of violation or corruption, j) Proactivity. Detect the scientific and technological demands of tomorrow, promoting productivity, competitiveness and environmental sustainability, k) Respect. To grant a dignified and cordial treatment to people and to our coworkers, considering their rights, promoting a courteous dialogue that leads to understanding, through efficiency and public interest, and l) Teamwork. Interdisciplinary work groups to meet the demands of society, through the generation of knowledge and integral technologies.

Finally, the institutional quality policy is based on promoting innovation with knowledge and technological solutions generated through research, which contribute to the sustainable development of agrifood chains and forestry systems, based on meeting the requirements and expectations of customers and stakeholders, fostering a culture of Total Quality. The Institute's most important resource is its personnel, since it is made up of a participative and co-responsible work team for the achievement of institutional objectives, in addition to contributing to sustainable rural development and providing technology, products and services of the highest level. It is worth mentioning that INIFAP is present throughout the Mexican Republic with a Central Office, 8 Regional Research Centers (CIR), 5 Disciplinary Research Centers (CENID), 38 Experimental Fields (CE), 39 Experimental Sites (SE), 42 Laboratories, and 3 Business Sites. INIFAP's institutional performance is based on the Results-Based Management Agreement, which is legally supported by Article 59 of the Law of Science and Technology, which states that the Public Research Centers (CPI) shall enter into Results-Based Management Agreements with the respective coordinating agency of the sector, in the case of INIFAP it is the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (AGRICULTURE); the National Council of Humanities, Science and Technology (CONHACyT) and the Ministries of Finance and Public Credit (HACIENDA) and of the Civil Service (FUNCIÓN PÚBLICA); which has the fundamental purpose of updating INIFAP's Results-Based Management Agreement 2020-2024, is to improve the Institute's activities, in order to reach the goals and achieve the programmed and agreed results, to have a more efficient and transparent performance and exercise of expenditure and accountability; as well as to link the results-based management with the budget assigned to it based on the Results-Based Budgeting (PbR) approach <https://www.gob.mx/inifap/documentos/desempeno-institucional-177385>. INIFAP employs 1901 people, distributed as follows: Certified personnel 884, trust personnel 128, base personnel (operational or field) 725 and middle and senior management personnel 164 respectively <https://www.gob.mx/inifap/documentos/inifap-en-cifras>. Regarding the base personnel (operative or field), it has been detected that more than 80% of them are already close to retirement age, which in the short term it is possible to have internal details in that institution since there will be a lack of research support personnel due to the fact that the current policies of the Federal Government are focused on working under the concept of outsourcing, so that the retirement positions will not be replaced in this institution.

Contextualization of INIFAP's operational-base personnel. INIFAP's operational-base personnel (field personnel) is a fundamental group for the development of the Institute's activities. These personnel are responsible for directly supporting researchers in order to carry out research, technology transfer and human resource training in the areas of agriculture, livestock, forestry and natural resources in rural areas, which vary according to the area of work and the specific project(s) in which they are working (Hernández et al., 2020). It is worth mentioning that these types of people play a fundamental role in the development of Mexico's agrifood and forestry sector. Their work is essential as support in the generation of scientific and technological knowledge, transferring technology to producers and training human resources committed to the development of the field (López and Pérez 2021). The main activities carried out by operational-base personnel (field personnel, are distributed in three main axes, which are research support activities, technology transfer support activities and human resources training support activities respectively (Martínez and González 2022).

Regarding research support activities, the following are described: a) Support in carrying out experiments: INIFAP operational-base personnel support in carrying out field and laboratory experiments to generate scientific and technological knowledge under real conditions; b) Support in data collection: INIFAP operational-base personnel collect field data on various aspects of agriculture, livestock, forestry and natural resources in the rural context; c) Support in data organization and analysis: INIFAP's operational-base staff supports in organizing and analyzes the collected field data for the responsible researcher to interpret the results and conclusions relevant to the agricultural sector. In the case of support for technology transfer activities, the following are described: a) Support in training producers: INIFAP's operational-base personnel (field personnel) supports the training of producers in the use of technologies developed by the Institute, adapting them to the specific needs and conditions of each region; b) Support in technical assistance: INIFAP's operational-base personnel provides personalized technical assistance to rural producers so that they can apply the technologies in their activities in an efficient and sustainable manner; c) Support in dissemination publications: INIFAP's operative-base staff supports in elaborating dissemination publications so that producers can access information in a simple way; and d) Support in field demonstrations: INIFAP's field staff supports in the organization of practical field demonstrations to show producers the advantages of new technologies and their application in the rural context. Finally, with regard to support activities in human resources training, the following are described: a) Collaboration in student training: INIFAP field personnel support in collaborating in the training of undergraduate, master's and doctoral students, providing them with the opportunity to carry out field practices in the various research in the rural area mainly; b) Support in thesis supervision INIFAP field personnel support in supervising the field work of activities concerning the theses of undergraduate, master's and doctoral students; and c) Support in the organization and execution of workshops and courses: INIFAP field staff contribute and support in giving workshops and courses to students, technicians and rural producers on various topics related to agriculture, livestock, forestry and natural resources (Martinez and Gonzalez 2022).

General information about the Cotaxtla-CIRGOC-INIFAP Experimental Field. The personnel who were interviewed by means of a recorded survey to learn about their retirement process through their Life Histories and who worked for more than 30 years at the Cotaxtla Experimental Field (CECOT), we consider that it is essential to mention some general aspects of this Experimental Field; in order to give the reader a general overview of the activities carried out there by the personnel under study.

This Experimental Field Cotaxtla (CECOT) was founded on December 4, 1954 by agreement between the Secretariat of Agriculture and Livestock and the Rockefeller Foundation, with the objective of generating agricultural technology to efficiently exploit the lands of the humid tropics of Mexico. In 1961 it became part of the National Institute of Agricultural Research (INIA) and since August 1985 it has belonged to the National Institute of Forestry, Agriculture and Livestock Research (INIFAP).

CECOT is located in the central region of the state of Veracruz and includes the Teocelo and Papaloapan Experimental Sites. It has a total area of 140 hectares, of which 6% are buildings such as offices, laboratories, roads, irrigation infrastructure, warehouses, greenhouses, seed processing plant, and cold rooms for seed storage, among others. There are currently 36 researchers, of whom 17 have doctoral degrees, 17 have master's degrees and 2 have bachelor's degrees, respectively. There are also 20 operational-base field personnel and 45 outsourcing personnel, respectively (own source).

The main research programs at the Cotaxtla Experimental Field are tropical fruit trees, corn, rice, beans, and chickpeas, Rice, Beans and Chickpeas, Sugarcane, Vegetables, Soil Fertility and Plant Nutrition, Socio-economics, Agro-meteorology and Modeling, Forest and Agricultural Health, Agroforestry Plantations, Bioenergy, Sustainable Forest Management and Environmental Services, Forest,

Livestock and Microbial Genetic Resources, Industrial and Perennial Crops, Integrated Watershed and Pasture Management and Forage Crops, respectively. It also has germplasm banks for mango, pineapple, orchids, cassava, pitahaya, coffee, soursop and other non-traditional tropical fruits with market potential. The main services offered by CECOT are the evaluation of the biological effectiveness of agrochemicals, evaluation of hybrids and varieties for the Plant Variety Qualification Committee (CCVP), training courses, International Diploma on Non-Traditional Tropical Fruits: INIFAP-JICA-SER and Course on Tropical Fruits for Japanese Scholars: INIFAP-SER-JAPAN. His main achievements in the last 15 years are the following: Development of improved varieties of corn, beans, sorghum and rice, Implementation of sustainable production systems, Control of pests and diseases using environmentally friendly methods, and Training producers in innovative agricultural techniques (own source). The Cotaxtla Experimental Field is a leading research center in the development of agricultural technologies for Mexico's humid tropics. Its work contributes to food security and rural development in the country; it is located at Km 34.5 of the Veracruz-Córdoba Federal Highway, municipality of Medellín de Bravo, Veracruz at coordinates 19° 14' 24" LN, 96° 09' 36" LO, with an altitude of 18 m. The climate is hot and humid with abundant rainfall in summer, an average annual temperature of 25 degrees Celsius and an annual rainfall of 1290 mm. The soils are mostly Vertisols, Cambisols and Luvisols respectively. (https://www.jica.go.jp/mexico/espanol/activities/agricultural_01.html).

Considerations to be taken into account for personnel about to retire from INIFAP

The National Institute of Forestry, Agriculture and Livestock Research (INIFAP), as a public institution of scientific and technological research in the agricultural field in Mexico, is governed by several laws and regulations, including the ISSSTE Law and its Regulations, which establish the guidelines and requirements for the retirement of operating personnel. Details of these laws and their regulations can be consulted at the following links: ISSSTE Law <https://www.diputados.gob.mx/LeyesBiblio/pdf/LISSSTE.pdf> and Regulations of the ISSSTE Law.

In this regard, according to INIFAP's Guidelines for the retirement of operational personnel (<https://www.gob.mx/inifap>), the general requirements for the retirement of this type of workers are as follows:

- Age: Comply with the minimum retirement age established by the ISSSTE, which is 60 years for men and 55 years for women.
- Contribution time: Accumulate a minimum of 30 years of contributions to ISSSTE.
- Weeks of contributions: Accumulate a minimum of 2,500 weeks of contributions to the ISSSTE.
- Definitive termination of work: To definitively stop rendering services at INIFAP.
- Proof of having performed operational functions for at least 15 years.
- Not to have been pensioned for disability or permanent disability.
- Not have been dismissed for just cause.

On the other hand, the procedure for initiating the retirement process for INIFAP's operational personnel:

- The interested worker must submit a formal request for retirement to the Human Resources area of INIFAP.
- The Human Resources area of INIFAP must verify that the employee meets the general and specific requirements for retirement.
- If the requirements are met, the INIFAP Human Resources area must prepare and deliver the ISSSTE Contribution Certificate to the employee.
- The employee must present the ISSSTE Contribution Certificate to initiate the retirement process.
- The ISSSTE will review the employee's documentation and issue the corresponding retirement decision.

Regarding the monthly income received by Inifap's retired operating personnel, it depends on several factors, so the amount received is different for each worker, since aspects such as base salary, contribution time, retirement age and retirement regime (ISSSTE 1973 or ISSSTE 2004) are considered; however, the process for calculating the net and gross income of each retired worker is mentioned below: 1. Calculation of the pension by contribution time: a) 1973 ISSSTE regime: The average of the highest base salaries of the last five years of service is calculated, multiplied by a pension factor that depends on the time of contribution, and b) 2004 ISSSTE regime: The average of the highest base salaries of the last 833 days of contribution is calculated, multiplied by a pension factor that depends on the time of contribution; 2. Pension calculation by age: a) ISSSTE 1973 Regime: The average of the

highest base salaries of the last five years of service is calculated, multiplied by a pension factor that depends on the retirement age and b) ISSSTE 2004 Regime: The average of the highest base salaries of the last 833 contribution days is calculated, multiplied by a pension factor that depends on the retirement age; 3. Minimum guaranteed pension: a) ISSSTE establishes a minimum guaranteed pension for all pensioners, which is updated annually; 4 Additional considerations: a) Type of retirement: The monthly pension may vary depending on the type of retirement (ordinary, disability or old age) and b) Widow(er)'s scale: In the event of the pensioner's death, his/her widow(er) spouse may be entitled to a widow(er)'s pension.

Situation of retirees in Mexico

According to data from the National Institute of Statistics and Geography INEGI, (2023), which is one of Mexico's autonomous constitutional bodies with its own management, legal personality and assets, responsible for regulating and coordinating the National System of Statistical and Geographic Information, there are 12.9 million people aged 60 and over in Mexico, of which 5.7 million are retirees, 63% are men and 37% are women, with an average pension of \$4,800 pesos per month for each retiree, respectively. According to CONSAR, (2023), the aforementioned figures are important because they show us the reality of retirement in Mexico, highlighting that the number of retirees is increasing year by year, pensions are not enough to cover the basic needs of many people and finally it is necessary to take measures to improve the situation of retirees in Mexico.

Importance of retirement in Mexico

Retirement in Mexico is an important stage in people's lives, as well as a fundamental right of all Mexican workers; it can be defined as a period of rest and tranquility after a life dedicated to work that allows the elderly to enjoy their free time and a dignified life (IMSS, 2023) and World Bank, 2023).

It is important for people to learn about the different retirement systems and to plan their retirement in advance for the following reasons: a) Economic security: Retirement provides a monthly income to older people, which allows them to cover their basic needs and maintain an adequate standard of living; b) Social well-being: Retirement allows older people to participate in social and cultural activities, which helps them to stay active and improve their quality of life; c) Mental health: Retirement can be a period of great personal satisfaction, as older people have the opportunity to enjoy their family, friends and hobbies; d) Enjoying leisure time: Retirement allows people to have more time for themselves, to do activities they enjoy and to spend time with family and friends; f) Learning new things: Retirement can be an opportunity to learn new things, to travel, to read, to study or to volunteer; and g) Sharing experiences: Retirement can be a time to share experiences with other older people, to participate in social and cultural activities and to contribute to the community (ISSSTE, 2023), (ILO, 2023) and (WHO, 2023). The different Retirement systems in Mexico are mentioned below: 1) IMSS Retirement System: This system is mandatory for all salaried workers who contribute to IMSS; 2) ISSSTE Retirement System: This system is mandatory for all state workers who contribute to ISSSTE; and 3) Afores: Afores are a private retirement savings system.

Mortality rate of retirees in Mexico and Veracruz.

According to official data from the National Institute of Statistics and Geography, 2023 (INEGI), the National Population Council, 2023 (CONAPO) and the Ministry of Health, 2023 (SSA), in Mexico the mortality rate of retired people according to various factors such as age because retired people are more likely to die than people of working age; sex because retired women have a higher life expectancy than retired men; health status because retired people are more likely to die than people of working age; sex because retired women have a higher life expectancy than retired men; health status because retirees with chronic diseases have a higher risk of dying than retirees in good health; socioeconomic status because retirees with higher income and education levels have a higher life expectancy than retirees with lower income and education levels; access to medicine because retirees with access to quality health care have a higher life expectancy than retirees with limited access to health care; and region of residence in Mexico. This template provides all the necessary information to the author regarding the formatting specifications needed for preparing electronic versions of their papers. We ask you to make your manuscript look exactly like this document. The easiest ways to do this is simply downloading the template, and replace (copy-paste) the content with your own material. All manuscripts must be in English. This document includes complete descriptions of the fonts, spacing, and related information for producing your proceedings manuscripts.

Margins, column widths, line spacing, and type styles are built-in; examples of the type styles are provided throughout this document and are identified in italic type, within parentheses, following the example. Some data from the aforementioned sources on mortality among retired individuals in Mexico are as follows:

- In 2020, the mortality rate for people aged 65 and over was 7.2 per 1,000 inhabitants.
- The leading causes of death among retired individuals are heart disease (20.9%), diabetes mellitus (14.5%), malignant tumors (13.2%), cerebrovascular diseases (7.4%), and liver diseases (4.5%).
- Life expectancy at birth for retired women is 81.2 years, while for retired men, it is 76.1 years.

On the other hand, regarding the mortality rate of retired individuals in the state of Veracruz, a similar trend to the national rate was found. For example, in 2020, the mortality rate for people aged 65 and over in Veracruz was 7.0 per 1,000 inhabitants, slightly lower than the national rate of 7.2 per 1,000 inhabitants. Additionally, life expectancy at birth for retired women in Veracruz is 80.7 years, while for retired men, it is 75.6 years. These figures are slightly lower than the national average. The leading causes of death among retired individuals in Veracruz are the same as those reported at the national level.

General Overview of Life Stories: Uses and Risks

Life stories, as a qualitative research methodology, have gained relevance in various fields of knowledge, including education, psychology, and sociology. Their origin dates back to the Chicago School of the 1920s, as noted by Goodson and Sikes (2001) in the first chapter of their work *Developing Life Histories*. These authors highlight that the Chicago School, a pioneer in qualitative research in the social sciences, recognized the value of life stories for understanding individual experiences and perspectives in specific social contexts (Goodson & Sikes, 2001). Throughout the 20th century, the methodology of life stories evolved alongside various academic movements, one of which was the linguistic-narrative turn, which emphasized the importance of language and narrative in the construction of knowledge and the understanding of social reality (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000). In this context, life stories have been valued for their ability to capture the richness and complexity of lived experiences, giving voice to the protagonists of these events (Flick, 2009). In this context, oral history has emerged as a complementary methodological approach to traditional history, based on the collection and analysis of oral testimonies to reconstruct the past from the perspective of the protagonists themselves (Portelli, 1998). This approach has been particularly fruitful in the study of marginalized or silenced groups in official history, providing a richer and more diverse view of the past (Thompson, 1990).

Life history as a particular dimension of oral history focused on biographical life narratives has established its position as a valuable methodology for historical and social research. In this sense, Pineau and Le Grand (1993) define it as "research and construction of meaning from personal temporal events," highlighting its potential to understand individual experiences within specific social contexts and to contribute to the construction of historical and social knowledge from a broader and more diverse perspective. While life narratives always refer to the uniqueness of a life, they reflect the social collectivity in question; as proposed by one of the pioneers of this methodology in Italy and France, it is possible to "read a society through a biography." Regarding the different uses of life histories in social sciences, Catani and Mazé (1982) already outlined in the introduction to their book seven categories of life narratives: a) Narratives of time-limited practices, b) Biographical sequences (various moments of life are inserted into a personal chronology), c) Biographical interviews or biographical narratives, d) Brief self-report of life history, e) Social life history, f) Biographical reconstruction, and g) Auto-bio-graphy.

The topic of life histories is applicable in any discipline. Examples of successful cases have been reported by Serret et al. (2015); Lopez et al. (2010); Mañas et al. (2019), where the first author published on life history in the training of early childhood education teachers, the second author published on the life history of good teachers: experiences and impact in the classroom, and the third author published on the life histories of people with intellectual disabilities. In other words, there are countless experiences under this approach of studying people from another perspective, which is extremely important because it provides a general and specific overview for the researcher conducting this activity and, at the same time, for the reader analyzing the published information.

Origin of life history methodologies. Life history methodologies have a complex and multifaceted origin, with roots in various intellectual traditions and social practices. That is, they are used in a wide range of disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, education, history, and cultural studies (Flick, 2014).

The main events that mark the historical development of life history methodologies are as follows:

- a) The biographical tradition: Since ancient times, biographies of important figures have been written both to celebrate their achievements and to understand their experiences and decisions. By the 19th century, biography had established itself as a literary genre with its own techniques and research methods.
- b) Social anthropology: In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, social anthropologists began using life histories as a tool to understand cultures and societies from the participants' own perspectives.
- c) Social psychology: Starting in the 1930s, social psychology began using life histories to study the development of personal identity and the influence of social context on individual experiences.
- d) Sociology: In the 1960s, sociology began using life histories to study social inequality and the experiences of marginalized groups.
- e) Feminism: From the 1970s onward, feminism has used life histories to give voice to women and understand gender experiences (Riessman, 2008).

Given the above, the objective of this document is based on recorded interviews with two retired individuals from the National Institute of Forestry, Agricultural, and Livestock Research (INIFAP), who were affiliated with the Cotaxtla Experimental Field (CECOT) - Gulf Central Regional Research Center (CIRGOC). Thankfully, these individuals are still alive and were able to provide the information required for this life history research on personnel who dedicated their entire working lives to INIFAP.

METHODOLOGY

Type of study

The research was conducted on the real-life histories of retired INIFAP personnel. It was framed within a naturalistic paradigm and a descriptive case study approach, based on qualitative data and focused on the life histories of two retired INIFAP employees. It is worth mentioning that the purpose of this research was to systematize and share the lived experiences of the participants through the lives of two retired INIFAP employees. The findings from these experiences are expected to serve as a foundation for other workers nearing retirement at INIFAP.

Participants

The study involved two retired INIFAP employees who were affiliated with the Cotaxtla Experimental Field. Both currently reside in the town of La Providencia, in the municipality of Medellín de Bravo, Veracruz. To conduct the interviews, it was necessary to visit their homes, where it was observed that both individuals were engaged in fieldwork activities at their residences. It is important to note that their participation was voluntary, and although they did not sign any documents, a close family member was present during the interviews to validate the recorded conversations. This was done primarily to share their life histories with the scientific community and, especially, with INIFAP personnel approaching retirement.

Instruments

For the development of this research, two instruments were used. The first was a printed script (questionnaire-type) with key questions related to the topic of interest, which in this study was the Life Stories of Retired Personnel from INIFAP. The second instrument was based on a recorded interview using a mobile phone, which focused on gathering information from the two participants/interviewees. The purpose was to systematize each interview and thereby understand the chronicle of their life stories to capture the initial reactions, feelings, and emotions experienced by the INIFAP retirees (Pereira, 2012). It is worth mentioning that the information provided by both instruments was transcribed verbatim and organized by phases for each interviewee, with the aim of identifying similar and divergent elements experienced and expressed through incomplete sentences.

Script Used for the Recorded Interview with INIFAP Retirees in Life Stories

1. General aspects of the interviewee to be asked to understand part of the typology of the retired person (LIFE STORY):
 - Full name
 - Address (locality, municipality, state)
 - Age
 - Education level
 - Marital status
 - Number of children

- Number of grandchildren
- Homeownership
- 2. Interview details
 - Why did you decide to retire? What were the reasons you considered for making that decision?
 - Was the decision to retire yours, made in agreement with your family, or were you forced to retire?
 - How did you feel when you started your retirement?
 - How old were you when you joined INIFAP, and how many years did you work at the institution?
 - What do you do now? Do you regret retiring? Also, were the activities you performed at INIFAP easier or harder than what you do now?
 - What were the advantages and disadvantages of retiring?
 - What did you do with your retirement settlement? And does your current monthly pension cover your needs?

Overview of the Recorded Interview on the Life Stories of INIFAP Retirees

The recorded interview with each participant lasted 20 minutes; however, afterward, there was a lengthy, detailed, and personalized conversation (off-camera) with each interviewee regarding more specific aspects related to the topic under study. It was observed that older individuals (over 60 years old), despite living in the 21st century, still exhibit a certain degree of fear toward technological advancements (recording). In these life stories, internal questioning was consistently identified among the interviewees. Based on their responses, most of them currently have mixed feelings about having made the decision to retire, as afterward, they lost all their benefits and only receive a pension based on their gross salary, which is significantly less than what they earned while active at INIFAP (Table 1). The two life story experiences are described later. In this regard, it is necessary to mention that two more individuals were planned to be interviewed. However, due to their current health conditions, it was no longer possible to interview them, as their families deemed it inappropriate. Out of professionalism, the situations described by the families were understood.

Table 1. General profile of the two interviewees on the life stories of INIFAP retirees

Indicators	Responses
Name:	Participant 1
Age:	68 years old
Address:	Ejido La Providencia, municipality of Medellín de Bravo, Veracruz.
Education level:	Completed primary school
Marital status:	Widowed
Number of children:	Three (Two daughters and one son)
Number of grandchildren:	Five grandchildren
Owns a house:	Yes
Name:	Participant 2
Age:	67 years old
Address:	Ejido La Providencia, municipality of Medellín de Bravo, Veracruz.
Education level:	Completed primary school
Marital status:	Married
Number of children:	Four (Three sons and one daughter)
Number of grandchildren:	Seven grandchildren
Owns a house:	Yes

Participant 1

I worked here at INIFAP for thirty full years... I decided to retire because, well, often it's about the economy, right? They gave me a good amount of money, and I decided to retire because they gave me a nice payout.

The decision to retire was discussed with my family. Yes, many times, well, they told us there was a retirement option, and in the end, we agreed and went ahead with it because they were going to pay me 100%, so, well, we took advantage of it and went ahead... my wife, she was part of this, and my children, and we all agreed and went ahead with the retirement. It was a family decision...

When I started my retirement, I felt very sad. You get used to being here, and suddenly you stop coming to work, so you feel sad, but what can you do? You have to move forward... I was 22 years old when I joined INIFAP...

Nowadays, well, I'm working here and there, doing odd jobs around the house and a bit of everything. You have to keep moving forward because if you don't, your body gets tired, you know? You have to stay active, active, so you can keep working. Sometimes I regret retiring, in a way, yes, because I feel sad, but what can I do? I have to move forward. Sometimes I feel a little down, but I keep myself busy with other things...

The work I did at INIFAP wasn't easy; it was more specific. There are some disadvantages to retiring because you no longer have the benefits you used to have. Once you're retired, they don't give you the same perks, you know? So, yes, there are some downsides, but I don't regret it. What's done is done. With the severance pay they gave me, I built my little house and maintained it, but money runs out, you know? Whereas a fixed salary, well, that's steady. Plus, the pension isn't enough; it's very little. But now, with the government support, we're getting by...

It's worth mentioning that Participant 1 regrets retiring at that time because he was still strong enough to work a few more years. Even at his age, he still does some fieldwork. Additionally, he lives relatively alone since his wife passed away a few years ago, and although his children live nearby, they don't visit him daily. He also mentions that he gets by with his pension and the support he receives from the federal government. His grandchildren, who visit him at least once a week, bring him a lot of joy.

Participant 2

I worked at INIFAP for over thirty years, as per the regulations. But you know, after that, I also worked as a temporary employee for several years, and then I decided to retire and rest. The decision wasn't easy because I thought about it a lot, but in the end, we made the decision with the family, and I went ahead to retire. I thought, "I'll have a secure pension every month," you know? Sometimes the family is right about everything because they give us ideas that we don't see on our own, and these decisions need to be discussed with the family...

When I retired, at first, it felt nice but strange at the same time because, well, you're used to being in the field, and suddenly you stop going, so it feels weird. But over time, you get used to being at home, right? Yes, like now. I still have a lot of work here; look, I'm growing beans and habanero peppers... It's worth mentioning that a few years after retiring—I don't remember if it was 4 or 5 years later—I had a heart attack that sent me to the hospital, and I was there for a long time. Thankfully, I recovered from that illness. Now I'm on treatment, and I've been feeling very well, thank God...

When I joined INIFAP, I don't remember exactly how old I was, but I was around 26 or so. I worked the required time to retire, which was over thirty years, you know? But after retiring, I continued working as a temporary employee in the Cotaxtla field for several more years...

Nowadays, I grow corn, beans, and whatever grows here, you know? And honestly, I don't regret retiring because I feel good, at peace, you know? I think having life now is what's important. Look at the time, and here we are, working hard, right? Yes. And besides, the weather here... Yes...

When I worked at INIFAP, I did tasks that we don't do daily here, and, well, you don't feel how fast time goes because one day you do one thing, the next day another, not always the same thing. The advantage of retiring is that I'm freer now, without the commitments from there. Here, I do what I can, you know? What I want, my own thing, without many obligations. I wake up whenever I want, you know? But fieldwork, well, you have to start early. There's work, and you have to be there early...

With the severance pay I received from my retirement, the first thing I did was build my little house. Yes, that's where the money went. And then, well, we managed to survive and get by. Nowadays, my pension isn't enough, but since we do other things here on our own, that helps, you know?...

I recommend to those close to retirement to think it through first because it's not just about completing the required years of work. It's not just about getting the money, you know? You have to fulfill the time, and in the end, if you have the opportunity for a pension, you should discuss it with your family, you know? I think family comes first; you have to consult with them so they understand, and later they don't say, "You left because you wanted to," you know?...

In this interview with Participant 2, it's clear that he is happy because, in addition to his pension and federal government support, he also earns income from growing corn, beans, habanero peppers, serrano peppers, bananas, and other crops near his house. His family lent him 1.0 hectare to farm year-round, and fortunately, he has an artesian well and water to irrigate his crops all year. This person doesn't regret retiring and enjoys his family very much. He says you have to live life to the fullest because it's beautiful.

CONCLUSIONS

Through this type of study, it was possible to address highly interesting topics, such as the motivations and satisfactions of retired personnel and, indirectly, their families, the challenges and obstacles they faced during and after their retirement, as well as the lessons learned during their productive years of service at the institution.

This study highlights the great importance of the work carried out by retired field workers of INIFAP, as they dedicated a significant part of their lives to the institution and are now reaping the rewards of what they sowed through their years of service. Furthermore, this type of study allows for a deeper understanding of aspects of the retirees' personal lives and their family members, which is a beautiful yet highly sensitive topic, as it touches on deeply personal aspects of the retirees and their relatives.

The study can contribute to fostering a stronger connection between retired field personnel and those who are nearing retirement. The lessons learned from retired personnel can be valuable for improving practices at INIFAP and for training new staff who will fill the positions left by these workers.

Finally, life stories can reveal experiences, emotions, values, and perspectives of retired personnel, providing a deeper understanding of their lives and work at INIFAP. Additionally, it can contribute to recognizing and valuing the important role of field personnel in the development of Mexico's agricultural and forestry sectors. It is worth emphasizing that the experiences and lessons learned from retired personnel can be useful for training new INIFAP staff and for improving institutional policies and practices.

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